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Observations on the floristic list of the Mersin collected from the highplateaus of Mersin

By

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Mersin University Research Herbarium (MERA) plants which are collected from Middle Taurus mountains are part of the Alpin-Himalayan system. In this research, the importance of these plants in terms of endemism and rare specimens is emphasized and they are compared with some of the Alpin and Himalayan plants.

MERA is presented for the first time. The 5000 sheets of specimens were collected between 1996-2009. Our results indicate that Asteraceae, Lamiaceae, Fabaceae, Poaceae are common families collected from the highplateaus in Gülnar, Bozyazı, Mut, Erdemli, Çamlıyayla and Tarsus province of Mersin.

Key words: Mersin plants; Taurus mountains, Meditteranean area (TURKEY).

INTRODUCTION

Figure 1. The Geographical Position of Research Area

Mersin is a city in the south of Turkey (Figure 1).

Türkiye, as a whole, houses more than 10 000 species of Spermatophyta, whose 33.3 (%) is endemics and which has many different types of vegetation. In Mediterranean Region, the Taurus Mountains support a high level of biodiversity, including a large number of endemic plants. Some 1710 of these endemics occur in the Bolkar Mountains in the middle of the Taurus range (Gemici 1994). *Astragalus*, *Verbascum*, *Centaurea*, *Galium*, *Alyssum*, *Stachys*, *Allium*, *Bupleurum*, *Tanacetum*, *Campanula*, *Anthemis*, *Silene*, *Arenaria*, *Sideritis*, *Salvia*, *Scrophularia*, *Alkanna*, *Crocus*, *Thlaspi*, *Veronica*, *Trigonella*, *Lathyrus*, *Onosma*, *Paracaryum*, *Crocus*, *Hieracium*, *Achillea*, *Hypericum*, *Fritillaria*, *Aethionema*, *Hyacinthella*, *Aristolochia*, *Phlomis*, *Nepeta*, *Thymus* are main endemic genera in Mersin (Babaç *et al* 1997).

There are a number of floristic and vegetation studies on the research area which covers the vegetation of Mut-Ermenek (Vural 1981), flora of Taşeli plateau (Sümbül and Erik 1988 a,b; 1990 a,b) and the flora of Bolkar mountains (Çamlıyayla, Gözne, Aslanköy highplateaus) (Gemici 1994). When we consider all of the researches, the most prevalent families contained in these researches are respectively, Asteraceae, Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, Brassicaceae, Poaceae, Caryophyllaceae, Apiaceae, Scrophulariaceae, Boraginaceae, Rosaceae, Liliaceae and Rubiaceae. These materials collected are housed in EGE, GAZI, ANK and AKDU.

Over 250 million plant specimens exist in more than 3000 herbaria in over 150 countries. Of all those specimens, only a small percentage has been inventoried and even a smaller percentage of these is available online (Krupnick *et al* 2008). MERA was established in 1996 and now 4931 vascular plants and 500 Cryptogamiae is preserved there. These plants belong to C4-C5 grid area.

Geology and History

Caves dating from 570 million years ago in Mersin (Aydıncık and Silifke) provide a definite evidence for the expansion of the Taurus Mountains during the late Miocene period. The range of mountains such as those of Bolkar, Aladağ and Geyik emerged from the Mediterranean sea as a result of tectonic pressure. Today, the Taurus Mountains are still in motion (Demirtaşlı *et al* 1975, Ünal *et al* 2001). Various kinds of marine fossils can be found on all of the high plateaus, but fossils of freshwater forms, eg. crocodile appear in some areas of Dalakderesi, Avkadı and Mut. Year by year, vertical tectonic movement in the Taurus Mountains has given rise to rich karstic formations. Canyons like Göksu were cut by giant rivers. Some of the important canyons such as Çömelek, Sason, Kubat and Kestel can reach up to almost 100m depth. Also, other important valleys are Cocak, Cacik and Göksu valleys.

Such valleys developed owing to the rise of the entire Taurus range from the sea, their rivers carved their beds early in the Quaternary period. Sometimes it is possible to estimate the depth of these rivers by investigating the cuts they have through the rock. In Mut, the Göksu river has cut a depth of 1000m, and the Cocak near Cehennemdere, to a depth of 1500m through the Dümbelek Plateau (Atalay 1994). The typical formation of the Taurus mountains are Miocene sediments with clay, marl and limestones derived from the sea.

Series of caves appear at 1000meters in various localities, including Çamlıyayla and Kozlar. In the Tertiary period, a tropical climate allowed the growth of *Pistacia*, *Quercus*, *Olea* and *Cistus*. Also in present, *Taxodium distichum* and *Liquidambar orientalis*, continue to flourish as plantation trees in Tarsus, Karabucak. A change to a colder climate occurred in the Quaternary period, as indicated by the arrival of *Carpinus orientalis*, *Cornus sanguinea* and *Taxus baccata* (Çamlıyayla) in the Mediterranean Region (Seçmen 1996).

The forest trees in Mersin highplateaus

Pinus brutia is widespread in Mersin. Also, the high plateaus have *P. nigra* in high level. Aslanköy, Abanoz, Güzeloluk, Bozyazı high plateaus, support the oldest forest of *Pinus brutia*. In the southern area, *Cedrus libani* has been living for a long time together with species of *P. nigra*.

In the region, the different forest trees include *Pinus brutia*, Junipers, *Pinus nigra var caramanica* (eg. in Mut), *Abies cilicica* (eg. in Ayvagediği: Karatepe), *Cedrus libani* (eg. in Mersin: Avgadı, Abanoz) and oaks. Differing from the other highplateaus, the maquis species, together with broad leaved forest species *Acer* and *Fraxinus* form a praedomaquis in Fındıkpinarı.

On the grazed slopes in the steppe sector, at altitudes around 2000meters, *Juniperus excelsa*, *J. foetidissima* are common. Generally, garrigue vegetation is common in the arid and damaged areas, at 50-100meters, typically including *Sarcopoterium spinosum*, *Cistus salvifolius*, *C. creticus* and *Thymus cilicicus*.

Quercus coccifera, with the shrub habitat, form the important microhabitats of the high plateaus in the Mediterranean region. *Q. coccifera* generates new forests and conserves the soil. Oaks on the Mersin highplateaus (Davis, 1985) including *Quercus cerris*, *Q. ithaburensis*, *Q. robur*, *Q. infectoria*, *Q. petrae*, *Q. coccifera* appear on all of the highplateaus. Among these, *Q. infectoria* appear at ca. 500m., in Güzeloluk and Balandız, *Q. ithaburensis* at ca. 800-900m in Balandız, Gülnar, Uzuncaburç and Kirobası, *Q. trojana* at 1000m in Mut, and *Q. cerris* at about 1000m in Aslanköy, Çamlıyayla, Gökbelen, Gülnar, Kirobası and Güzeloluk; and *Q. petrae* is observed as dispersed trees in the all of the highplateaus.

The relationship of the people to the forests

The people of the high plateaus engage in animal breeding, agriculture and forestry. The microclimate zones allow the growth of oranges, kiwi and *Diospyros kaki* fruits and various vegetables, such as in Aslanköy, Sutras.

Grazing is particularly prevalent on the alpine slopes because it is a traditional practice in the world. The herdsmen reach the different alpine zones from the middle of March to September and during this period most of the young plants are eliminated from these areas because of premature grazing. The nomadic people live in stone shelters or tents "çadır", just like "yurt" in Kyrgyz, while their flocks seek the cover of oak trees.

Sometimes, owing to the climate or the need for veterinary attention, the flocks will be brought down the mountain for a short time.

It seems that, in undisturbed areas, some of the shrubs which grow in open areas can become to form tall trees, for example, *Q. coccifera* in Aslanköy and Çamlıyayla. Against destroying forests, one of the preventive plans by the Forest Ministry is to increase the number of nursery-gardens (Baki *et al* 1998). Also, in the last years, different "memory forests" are developed by the Forest Ministry and tracking activities, trips and camping facilities are organised. One of the tracking centres is Medetsiz summit (3524 m) in the Bolkar Mountains.

Also, these areas of biodiversity are conserved by the General Directorate of Ministry of Forestry (Orman Genel Müdürlüğü 1999): Conservation area of the wild goats of Çağlarca and Gökbelen: Hisardağ Karakaya-Göksu, Cocak-Cehennemdere and Mut: Alahan, Kestel, Göksu Delta Conservation area, Conservation area of the *Perdix perdix*: Anamur: Kızılaliler, Sarıaliler, Sarıyayla Conservation area of *Capreolus capreolus*: Anamur: Sugözü.

Erdemli pine plantations, the Alata research center, Hundreth century Conservation Park, City Forest and Kayacı valley are famous recreation centres in Mersin. Also, Gülek, Karboğaz area in Mersin was reorganized for tourism in 2008. It is clear that the original forest cover (red pines, oaks, fir, junipers, cedar) has existed from the ancient geological periods to the present day. In ancient times, the felling of timber for foreign export has destroyed much of the vegetation in Mersin than in Adana.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this research, in general the observations of the collected plants from Mersin highplateaus (Middle Taurus Mountains) is presented. These plants are housed in MERA in Biology Department. The plant species were identified according to Davis (1985) and Güner *et al* (2000).

The climate is generally Mediterranean, with hot summers and mild winters (Met. gen. bull. 1974). The Taurus Mountain range tends to have wet winters and dry summers, with an average annual rainfall of 750-1350 mm. Most of the total rainfall in the mountains occurs as snow in winter or smog (in summer and winter). Within this general pattern of rainfall there are wide local variations. The alpine level has a slightly terrestrial climate. Rainfall is surely the most important factor after altitude as an influence on the composition of the high plateaus flora. In both winter and summer, the research area experiences long hours of daylight.

Research area

Mersin contains about 64 high plateaus. High plateaus is known as 'yayla' in Turkey. They have many visitors in Summer, but in winter they are generally populated only by local people. In spring, the people like to move from their villages to the high steppe areas. The names of some localities in the highplateau reflect the nature of their vegetation. Examples include Daffodil Mount, Pine Valley, Yellow Water, etc. Additionally, names like Red Mountain, Red Area, Red Vineyard refer to the colour of the Mediterranean soil.

The research area is in the Mediterranean region of Turkey and extends westward from the Taşeli plateau to Ceyhan River, and northward, from the coast to the middle Taurus Mountains. The phytogeography of Mersin is influenced by Bolkar and Geyik Mountains. Several wetlands, such as Bakır, Göksu, Lamas, Deliçay and Berdan which contain many significant migration routes of birds, play an important role in the ecological stability of southern Turkey. Furthermore, Mediterranean, Irano-Turanien and relic Euro-Siberian elements grow in the research area (Figure 1). In this area, especially the riversides of Anamur, Bakır, Göksu, Lamas, Berdan and Deliçay contain new recorded plants such as *Flueggea anatolica* from Berdan riversides in Çamlıyayla; Yalamık village (Gemici 1994) and *Jurinea cyprea* in Göksu riversides.

Mersin Highplateaux

Tarsus: Gülek, Namrun (Çamlıyayla) (1500 m), Sebil, Hangediği,
Mersin: Gözne, Soğucak (800 m), Ayvagediği (1500 m), Kızılbağ, Fındıkpinarı (1100 m), Aslanköy (1350 m), Mihrican, Haçgediği,
Erdemli: Avgadı (900 m), Güzeloluk (1100 m), Sorgun (1600 m), Dedeli (2000 m); Küçükfindık, Toros (1600 m), Hacıalanı, Pınarbaşı, Güneyli,
Silifke: Balandız (900 m), Gökbelen, Çaltız,
Gülnar: Bardat (1450 m), Tersakan, İlisulu, Bozyazı: Kozağaç
Mut: Kozlar (1450m), Göğden (1990m), Kirobası (Mara), Sertavul (1400m),
Anamur: Abanoz (1629 m), Sarıdana, Kaş (1600 m), Halkalı, Berem, Gözlügöl, Kayagöl, Akpınar (1634 m), Beşkuyu, Çukurbağ, Armutkırı (1400 m), Kayıhan, Elbalak (2000 m.), Tandır, Örcüölük (Everest 2001).

The soil types of Mersin

With the effect of climate, topography and plant vegetation, major soil groups have developed in the highplateaux in the following ways:

1. Colluvial soils: The accumulation soils on the sides of hills and deep valleys can be seen at different altitudes
2. Brown forest soils: Basic materials with high CaCO_3 content can be seen later Mersin-Tarsus Redzinal soil and continuous the boundary of Konya ,is separated from the villages and have a high limestone content.
3. Non-limestone brown forest soils: On the serpentine, crystalline CaCO_3 , under the forest and shrubs. Poor in CaCO_3 Brown soils: Vicinity of Adana: Tufanbeyli, Kahramanmaraş and Niğde are the boundary.
4. Red Mediterranean soils: From the northeast of Silifke extends north of Erdemli to the boundary of Konya and contains ferric ions (Fe^{+3}).
5. Red brown Meditteranean soils: the low altitude, and flat areas than from Red Mediterranean soils on cement, crystal cancer, pebble materials develop (Köy Hizmetleri 1991).

Altitudinal variation in vegetation in Mersin

Maquis vegetation: *Ceratonia siliqua*, *Olea europea*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Arbutus andrachne*, *Rhamnus oleides*, *Quercus coccifera*, *Myrtus communis*, *Euphorbia macroclada*, *Laurus nobilis*, *Calycatome villosa*, *Paliurus spinachristii*, *Styrax officinalis*, *Phyllaria latifolia*, *Cistus creticus*,

Hygrophly vegetation: *Mentha*, *Tussilago*, *Parnasia*, *Clematis*, *Pulicaria*, *Veronica*, *Calamintha*, *Verbena*, *Vitex*, *Ranunculus spp.*

Edge of roads vegetation: *Papaver*, *Fumaria*, *Arabis*, *Nasturtium*, *Lepidium*, *Alyssum*, *Circium*, *Carduus*, *Echinops*, *Echium*, *Scolymu spp.*

Open areas: *Ajuga*, *Teucrium*, *Stachys*, *Salvia*, *Thymus*, *Ziziphora spp.*

Forest vegetation: *Juniperus excelsa*, *J. drupaceae*, *Cedrus libani*, *Abies cilicica*, *Pinus nigra*, *P. brutia*

Galery forest: *Salix*, *Populus*, *Platanus*, *Alnus spp.*

Grass vegetation: *Hypericum*, *Geranium*, *Erodium*, *Vicia*, *Trifolium*, *Bellis*, *Anthemis*, *Cichorium*, *Scorzonera*, *Taraxacum*, *Chondrilla*, *Myosotis*, *Anchusa*, *Galium*, *Rubia*, *Ornithagalum*, *Prunella*, *Muscari*, *Crocus*, *Allium spp.*

Rocky vegetation: *Umbilicus*, *Mathiola*, *Sedum*, *Onosma*, *Daphne*, *Primula*, *Cyclamen*

The high mount vegetation: *Cerastium*, *Dianthus*, *Helichyrsom*, *Cyperus spp.*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Alpine-Himalayan unit, the central and eastern Bolkars of Taurus Mountains are rich as endemics, while some of them, (eg. local endemic *Lamium garganicum* subsp. *pulchrum*,) live in and around Aslanköy. The others, such as *Alkanna aucherana*, *Stachys rupestris*, *Arisarum vulgare* and also *Alkanna kotschyana*, which has penetrated Mersin and Adana, grow among ruins near the seaside Mersin, Kızıkalesi.

The total of 376 endemic plants such as *Lamium garganicum* subsp. *pulchrum* (Aslanköy), *Verbascum microcephalum* (Anamur: Akpınar), *Astragalus goeznensis* (Gözne), *Galium cilicicum* (Mut) and *Quercus petrea* subsp. *pinnatiloba* (Balandız) are recorded from the Mersin region alone. Mersin shows about 20% -endemism ratio in Taşeli plateau, Mut line and Bolkars of Middle Taurus Mountains. In this area, endemic trees such as *Amgdalus zielinskii*, *Quercus petrea* subsp. *pinnatiloba*, *Pyrus syriaca* and also flowering plants such as *Astragalus*, *Verbascum*, *Centaurea*, *Galium*, *Alyssum* and *Stachys* can be seen.

Meanwhile Mersin Research Herbariums records can preserve these endemic plants by Red List categories (Ekim *et al* 2000): LR (nt) 64 sp., LR (cd) 27 sp, LR (lc) 148 sp, VU 46 sp, EN 22 sp, DD 11 sp ve CR 5 sp. The categories given as not only endemic but also rare species were total of 5 of DD, 6 of VU and 1 EN (Ekim *et al* 2000). As rare species *Spinacia tetrandra* DD, *Halopeplis amplexicaulis* EN, *Astragalus drusorum* var. *maroniticus* VU, *Potentilla libatonica* DD, *Erica sicula* ssp. *libatonica* VU, *Stachys inflata* VU, *Calamintha betulifolia* DD, *Citrullus colocynthis* VU, *Gentiana brachyphylla* subsp. *favrotti* DD, *Potentilla libanotica* DD, *Zygophyllum album* VU and *Scilla silicica* VU are collected in Mersin.

Table 1. The general families which contain endemic species in Middle Taurus:

Families	Bolkar mounts (Gemici 1994)	Mut-Silifke (Everest <i>et al</i> 2003)	Anamur- Gülнар (Özer and Everest 2008)	Sorgun- Erdemli (Yüceol <i>et al</i> 2009)
Lamiaceae	33	21	9	6
Fabaceae	35	6	3	3
Asteraceae	28	5	9	9
Brassicaceae	24	3	2	5
Scrophulariaceae	24	9	11	1
Caryophyllaceae	22	3	1	4
Apiaceae	16	1	3	2
Boraginaceae	12	9	2	1
Liliaceae	9	1	2	1
Rubiaceae	7	1	1	1
Campanulaceae	5	3	2	1
Hypericaceae	2	2	1	1
Total	1647 spp.	667 spp.	676 spp.	608 spp.

Table 2. The comparison of the some genera with other areas:

Genera	Middle Taurus	Medit..Alps (Everest 2001)	Himalayas Dobremez <i>et al</i> 2000)
Astragalus	1.54	-	3.89
Veronica	1.54	-	3.89
Bromus	1.85	2.58	-
Euphorbia	1.39	2.58	3.61
Stachys	1.23	2.11	-
Centaurea	1.23	1.87	-
Campanula	1.23	3.75	-
Orchis	1.23	1.87	-
Geranium	1.23	3.52	1.55
Medicago	0.92	1.64	-
Thymus	0.77	2.81	-
Arenaria	0.61	-	3.68
Alyssum	0.61	-	0.99
Galium	0.61	1.87	1.55
Myosotis	0.46	1.64	-
Total	16.45	31.86	19.16

Table 3. The comparison of the families with other research areas:

Mountains	end. (%)	Ast.	Poa.	Fab.	Brass.	Lam.	Car.	Ros.	Scr.	Api.	Lil.	Total spp.
Çakmak (Gümüüş, 1992)	6.5	10.5	9.7	6.6	6.3	6.6	5.5	5.8	-	4.7	-	318
Tahir (Gümüüş, 1992; 2007)	9	13.2	8.8	8.1	6.9	6.1	5.6	5.1	4.6	3.8	3.3	758
Hazar (Yurdakulol&Altan, 1984)	9.7	12.3	6	12.9	7.4	6.1	6.2	5	-	4.7	-	603
Süphan (Behçet, 1990)	8.7	15.6	9.2	10.3	7.2	6.9	5.1	4.2	3.5	4.4	3.2	780
Bağırba (Kaya, 1996)	6.5	11	7.7	9.5	7	8.3	4.8	4.8	2.9	3.6	-	862
Erek (Özçelik, 1987)	0.5	15.7	10.8	10	5	7.9	4.1	3.8	-	5	3	260
Munzur (Yıldırımli, 1995)	19.9	12.1	5.0	8.7	9.2	7.2	5.7	-	4.0	4.2	4.3	1518
Middle Taurus (Table 1)	11	15	11.5	10.7	4	11.5	5.4	2.1	4.5	2.4	4.6	933
Medit. Alps (Everest 2001)	-	23	15	18.5	3.5	6.6	4.4	5	1	2	1.9	939
Himalayas Dobremez <i>et al</i> (2000)	-	15	11.8	9.3	4.3	4.9	4.1	6.5	4.6	-	2.4	8772

The Alps are famous for their rich and multi coloured flora, estimated in approx. 4500 different species: more than 500 are exclusive of the Alps, 180 species are endemic of the Western Alps and the other 70 species widely spread over the mountain range. Some areas of the Western Alps are rich in flora; in the Liguria and Maritime Alps 2660 different species accounting for 60 % of the French flora could be found (<http://www.whc.unesco.org>).

The flora of the mountains of Central Asia, is a mix of Boreal, Siberian, Mongolian, Indo-Himalayan and Iranian elements. There are more than 5500 known species of vascular plants in the hotspots of which about 1500 are endemic while only Bolkars have 1710 endemics. Likewise, vegetation of Afganistan have 5000 species and 20-30 % of these species are endemics (Kaul 1997, Muratgeldiyev *et al* 2007, Ballabh *et al* 2007). *Juglans regia*, *Amgdalus communis*, *Cerasus mahaleb* and *Pyrus*, *Prunus*, *Acer species* grow in the steppe and meadow zones of the mountains Tien Shan and Taurus.

Asiatic elements are maximum in Himalaya highplateaux however, there are also Irano-Turanien and Meditteranean elements such as *Alopecurus*, *Aegilops*, *Euphorbia*, *Orobancha*, *Cotoneaster*, *Bunium*, *Arnebia*, *Gagea* and *Alyssum*. The alpine meadow type is found in valley floors and hill slopes; these are *Polygonum*, *Carex*, *Anemone*, *Gentiana*, *Ranunculus*, *Potentilla*, *Elymus*, *Primula*, *Galium*, *Festuca*, *Poa*, *Stipa* which can appear together with steppic plants such as *Astragalus* and *Oxytropis*.

On the river sides, there are *Populus*, *Salix*, *Juglans*, *Fraxinus*, *Berberis*, *Pyrus* and *Acer*. Moreover, on valley floors with sand dunes, there are *Artemisia*, *Berberis*, *Ephedra*, *Origanum*, *Salicornia* and *Tamarix* shrubs. *Origanum*, *Achillea*, *Artemisia*, *Geranium*, *Euphorbia*, *Allium*, *Salvia*, *Clematis*, *Campanula* and *Silene* are common and widespread plants in Toluk valley (Everest and Türker 2009). As can be seen in the Polunin' s floristical list, *Asteraceae* and *Fabaceae* are principle families in Himalaya highplateaux, and other the most common families are *Orchidaceae*, *Lamiaceae*, *Brassicaceae*, *Liliaceae*, *Rosaceae* (Polunin 1999). However, these results are changeable due to the number of the collected materials. For example, *Asteraceae* and *Poaceae* are presented as an example of the principle families in the research of Savoie University (Dobremez *et al*, 2000). Also, it is possible to find some differences in the most of the genera in Polunin' s list.

As Allendorf pointed out that over 100 000 protected areas accounted for 12 % of the world's land area and these protected areas were seen as a key strategy to conserve diversity. If protected areas are to be conserved over the long term, management must address local residents' concerns and integrate them into management strategies (Allendorf 2007).

Generally, the main risk of the highplateaux are pasturage and settlement, also cutting down trees and burning some shrubs. The subalpine and alpine zone of Central Alps has probably been changed by grazing which can be seen by the growth of such plants as *Mutellina*, *Scorzonera* and *Lotus* which are the indicators of this change (Meyer *et al* 2008).

Biological reserve areas of Middle Taurus, such as Çamlıyayla, Anamur, Gülnar and Erdemli highplateaus with forest and relic areas should be protected. Environmental values of these highplateaus provide the clean water, wildlife and recreation activities. Natural and cultural values of these highplateaus provide not only economic benefits, but also quality of life values cherished by many.

In substance, MERA (Mersin University Research Herbarium), built in 1996, contains a total number of about 5000 plants. These plants symbolize the highplateaus.

The sample plants most similarly reflect the highplateaus of Mersin, as well as the Beşparmak Mountains of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, Nice Maritime Alps and Mediterranean region. And it contains a wide number of samples of the Alpine-Himalayan-Taurus Mountain range.

By gathering wide range of samples from both local and overseas travels, research projects and graduate theses, MERA has been formed in years. We hope that the introduction & presentation of this herbarium abroad, may be first realised.

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REFERENCES

- Atalay, İ. (1994). Türkiye Vejetasyon Coğrafyası. Ege Ün. Basımevi. İzmir. 352 s.
- Avcı, M. (2005). Çeşitlilik ve Endemizm Açısından Türkiye' nin Bitki Örtüsü. İstanbul Ün. Edebiyat Fakültesi. Coğrafya Dergisi. İstanbul. 13: 27–55.
- Babaç, M., Bilgin C. and Usta, E. (1997). Türkiye Herbaryumları Merkezi Veri Tabanı. TÜBİTAK kesin proje raporu. (www.tubitak.gov.tr/tubives)
- Baki, G., Güler, M. and Erdem, V. B. (1998). Cumhuriyet Döneminde Ormanlarımız. Orman Genel Müdürlüğü basımı. Adana. 111 s.
- Ballabh, B. and Chaurasia, O.P. (2007). Traditional medicinal plants of cold desert Ladakh-Used in treatment of cold, cough and fever. Journal of Ethnopharmacology. 112 (2): 341-349.
- Behçet, L. (1990). Phytosociological Studies on the Stepe Communities of Süphan mountains (Bitlis) Yüzüncü Yıl Univ. Yayınları. C. 1., S. 1, Van.
- Canadel, J. and Vila, M. (1992). Variation in tissue element concentrations in *Q. ilex* L. over a range of different soils. Vegetatio. 99-100: 273-282.
- Casazza, G., Barberis, G. and Minutol, L. (2005). Ecological Characteristics and rarity of endemic plants of the Italian maritime Alps. Biological Conservation. 123(3): 361-371.
- Coste, H. (1937). Flore Descriptive et Illustrée, De la France, 1: 416, 2: 627, 3: 807, Paris: Librairie Scientifique et Technologie.
- Davis, P.H. (1985). Flora of Turkey and the East Aegean Islands. Vol:1-10, Edinburg Univ. Press. Edinburg.
- Demirtaşlı, E., Bilgin, A.Z. Selim, M. and Turhan, N. (1983). Geology of the Bolkar Mountains, Geology of Taurus Belt Symp. Maden Tetkik ve Arama Ens. Derg. 125–143.
- Dobremez, J.F., Shakya, P.R., Vigny, F., Camaret, T.S. and Mchet, R.E. (2000). Dynamism Laboratory of the university of Savoie. In the website of the Altitude of Ecosystems. (<http://www.lsh.univ-savoie.fr/sc/form.asp>.)
- Ekim, T., Koyuncu, M., Vural, M., Duman, H., Aytaç, Z. and Adıgüzel, N. (2000). Türkiye Bitkileri Kırmızı Kitabı (Eğrelti ve Tohumlu Bitkiler). 246 s.
- Everest, A. (2001). The excursion in the Maritime-alps of Nice. Phytologia Balcanica. 7: 3.
- Everest, A. (2001). Osmaniye, Adana ve İçel Yaylaları İle Genel Vegetatif Yapıları. Yankı ofset. Mersin. 90 s.
- Everest, A., Kılıç, H. and Uçar, H. (2003). The flora of Mersin: Balandız-Gökbelen-Bardat Highplateaus, south Turkey, Bothanica Chronica, 16: 61-95.
- Everest, A. and Türker, N. (2009). Observations the floristical of the canyons, Uluslar arası Çevre Sempozyumu, 20-23mayıs. Bişkek. Kırgızistan.
- Feinborn, D.N. (1978). Flora Palaestina, the Israel Academy of Sciences and Humanities. Jerusalem Academic Press. 481 pp.
- Freres, V. (1930). Flor edu Liban et De La Syrie. Atlas de 512 plances, publication, publication subventionnee parle Ministere des Affaires Etrangeres, Le Ministere de l'Instruction Publique. l' Academie des Sciences. Le Gouvernement de la Republique Libanaise. 508 pp.
- Frumin, S. and Shammash, B. (2009). Types of the Anthemis in the Herbarium of the Hebrew University of Jaruselam (HUJ). Israel Jour. of Science. 86(3): 279-293.

- Gemici, Y. (1994). Bolkar Dağları Flora ve Vegetasyonu Üzerine Genel Bilgiler. *Doğa Türk Botanik Dergisi*. 18(2): 81-89.
- Güner, A., Özhatay, N., Ekim, T. and Başer, K.C.H. (2000). Flora of Turkey and the East Aegean Islands. Edinburg Univ. Press. Edinburg. 656 pp.
- Gümüş, İ. (1992) Çakmak Dağları (Ağrı) Florasına Giriş, *Doğa Türk Botanik*, 16, 54-70.
- Gümüş, İ. (2007). Flora of Güzeldere Valley-Tahir Mountains (Ağrı) and Comparison with Studies Made in the East Anatolia, *Erzincan Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi Cilt-Sayı: 9-1*.
- Gümüş, İ. (1992). Tahir Dağları ve Güzeldere Havzası (Ağrı) Step Vegetasyonunun Bitki Sosyolojisi Yönünden Araştırılması, *Doğa, Tr., J., of Botany*, 16, 153-175.
- Harita Genel Komutanlığı. (1990). Harita Genel Komutanlığı İçel Harita Serisi. Ankara.
- Kaya, Y. (1996). Tercan Çevresi ile Şengül (Erzincan) ve Bağırbaşa (Tunceli) Dağlarının Florası, *Doğa Türk Botanik Dergisi*, 20, 1, 75-98.
- Kaul, M.K. (1997). Medicinal plants of Kashmir and Ladakh Temperature&cold&arid Himalaya. Indus publishing. New Delhi. India. 173 pp.
- Krupnick, G.A., Kress, J.W. and Wagner, L. (2008). Archiving Target 2 of the Global Strategy for plant Conservation: building a preliminary assesment of cascular plant species using data from Herbarium specimens. *Biodivers Conserv.*
- Meteoroloji Genel Müdürlüğü (1974). Ortalama ve ekstrem değerler bülteni. 383-384.
- Meyer, R. Kaufman, R. Vorhauer, K. Erschbamer, B. (2009). Effects of Grazing exclusion on species composition in high altitude grasslands of the Central Alps. *Basic and Applied Ecology*. article in press.
- Miko, L. (2007). Europe's endangered plants –challenges for conservation. *Natura* 2000. no: 23.
- Muratgeldiyev, Y., Küçükökdük, M., Bingöl, Ü., Güney, K. and Geven, F. (2000). Iran-Turan Floristik Bölgesi. S. Ü. Fen-Edebiyat Fakültesi Dergisi. 1:119-124.
- Orman Genel Müdürlüğü (1999). Yıllık Bülten. Ankara.
- O'Sullivan and A. Kelly, L.D. (2006). A recent History of sessile oak (*Quercus petrae*)-dominated woodland in Killarney, S.W. Ireland, based on tree-ring analysis. *Biology and Environment*. 106(3): 355-370.
- Yüceol, F., Öztürk, E. and Everest, A. (2009). Batı Sandal-Büyük Sorgun (Mersin: Erdemli) arasındaki bölgenin floristik yapısı. *Biyoloji Bilimleri Araştırmalar Dergisi*. 2(1): 17-31.
- Özçelik, H. (1987). Erek Dağı (Van) Vegetasyonu Üzerinde Fiteokolojik Araştırmalar. *Çevre, Başbakanlık, Çevre Gen. Müd.*, 4, 3-15.
- Özer, E. and Everest, A. (2008). Kozağaç yaylasının (Mersin: Bozyazı/Türkiye) floristik yapısı, Mersin Sempozyum Bildiri kitabı. Mersin.
- Polunin, O. and Stainton, A. (1999). Flowers of the Himalaya, Oxford Univ. Press, 580 p.
- Parisod, C. (2008). Postglacial recolonisation of plants in the western Alps of Switzerland, *Bot. Helv.* 118 (2008): 1 – 12
- Prashant K. Pusalkar and D. K. Singh. 2010. *Sageretia santapau* sp. nov. and *S. devendrae* sp. nov. (Rhamnaceae) from western Himalaya, India. *Nordic Journal of Botany*. 28:1 (49 – 53).
- Seçmen, Ö. (1996). Türkiye Florası. Ege Üniversitesi. Fen Fakültesi Teksirler serisi. İzmir. 84 s.
- Sümbül, H. and Erik, S. (1988 a): Taşeli platosu florası I. *Türk Botanik Dergisi*. 12(2): 175-205.
- Sümbül, H. and Erik, S. (1988 b): Taşeli platosu florası II. *Türk Botanik Dergisi*. 12(3): 254-322.
- Sümbül, H. and Erik, S. (1990). Taşeli platosu florası III. Hacettepe Ün. Fen ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi. 11: 1-38.
- Sümbül, H. and Erik, S. (1990). Taşeli platosu florası IV. Hacettepe Ün. Fen ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi. 11:61-120.
- Sheehy, D.P. Miller, D. And Johnston, D.A. (2006). Transformation of traditional pastoral livestock systems on the Tibetan steppe. *Science et changements planetaries/Secheresse*. 17:142-151. States to the Convention as of Apr 16. 2009: 1. <http://whc.unesco.org>
- T.C. Tarım Orman ve Köy İşleri Bakanlığı (1991). İçel (Mersin) ili arazi varlığı. Köy Hizmetleri Genel Müdürlüğü yayınları. Ankara. 11:33.
- Uslu, T. (1977). A plant ecological and sociological research on the dune and maquis vegetation between Mersin and Silifke. *Comm. Fac. Sci. Univ. Ank. Ser. 2: 21. supp. 4-5(1):1-60*.
- Ünal, A. Atabey, E. and Saraç, G. (2001). Small Mammals and Foreminifera from the Anatolian (Central Taurus) Early Miocene. *Ann. of Garnegie Museum*. 70(4):247-256.
- Vargas, P. and Garcia, B. (2008). Plant Endemics to Sierra de Gredes (Central Spain): taxonomic, distributional and evolutionary aspects. *Anales del Jardin botanico de Madrid*. 65 (2): 353-366.
- Vural, M. (1981). Mut-Ermenek-Karaman arası orman-step geçiş bölgesinin fitososyolojik yönden araştırılması. *Selçuk Ün. Fen Bil. Ens. Konya*. 122 s.
- Wong, K.M., Sugumara, M. and Lee, D.K.P. (2008). Ecological Aspects of Endemic Plant Populations on Klang Gates quartz, ridge, a habitat island in peninsular Malasia. *Biodivers Conserv.* 13pp.

- Yıldırım, Ş. (1997). The chorology of the Turkish species of Acanthaceae, Aceraceae, Aizoaceae, Amaranthaceae and Anacardiaceae families. OT Sistematik Botanik Dergisi. 4 (1): 125-133.
- Yurdakulol, E., Altan, Y. (1984). Contribution to the Flora Hazar Mountains (Elazığ), De la Faculté des sciences de l'université D'Ankara, Serie C, Tome: 2. Ankara.
- Yıldırım, Ş. (1995). Flora of Munzur Dağları (Erzincan-Tunceli). OT Sistematik Botanik Dergisi. 2 (1): 1-78.
- <http://www.frlht.org.in/htm/herbarium.htm>
- <http://www.bgbm.org/herbarium/access.cfm>
- <http://www.botany.ch/herbaria.htm>
- http://www.nice.fr/mairie_nice_921.html
- <http://www.herb.gazi.edu.tr>
- <http://www.izef.ege.edu.tr>
- <http://www.vanherbaryum.yyu.edu.tr/flora>
- <http://www.glti.nrcs.usda.gov/wps/portal/nrcs/main/national/landuse/rangepasture>